

Maternal Coping strategies in oral care of special children- a review

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Abstract

American Health Association defines a child with disability as a child, who, for various reasons, cannot fully make use of all his or her physical, mental, and social abilities. These children have some typical characteristics which include serious learning difficulties, use of specific behavioural strategies to avoid learning opportunities, attention deficits and communication problems. Down syndrome is a congenital autosomal anomaly which is characterized by generalized growth and mental deficiency. Cerebral palsy is a condition caused by damage to the brain, usually occurring before, during or shortly after birth. Epilepsy is a disease that involves seizures which are characterized by an alteration of perception, behavior and mental activities, as well as by involuntary muscle contractions, temporary loss of consciousness and chronic changes in neurological functions that result from abnormal electrical activity in the brain. Autism spectrum disorders (ASDs) are lifelong neuro-developmental disabilities that begin in infancy and impair communication and social behaviours. Parents of children with developmental disorders experience high levels of stress, health problems, loss of feeling responsible and defect in physical functions, and fatigue or burnout.

Keywords: Maternal Coping, Special Children, Quality Of Life, Down Syndrome, Cerebral Palsy, Epilepsy, Autism.

INTRODUCTION

According to World Health Organization, children with disabilities in overall world comprise 10% of the total population in developed countries and 12% in developing countries (Baykan, 2003). American Health Association defines a child with disability as a child, who, for various reasons, cannot fully make use of all his or her physical, mental, and social abilities (Bernier, 1994). For parents raising a child with special care needs is a big challenge. Such children are unable to perform their daily activities individually. The specific features of these children, constitutive for child-parent interaction patterns, were well described in empirical literature in the previous years which gives an idea of their scale of psychology and understanding. These children have some typical characteristics which include serious

learning difficulties, use of specific behavioural strategies to avoid learning opportunities, attention deficits and communication problems.

Children with disabilities have been observed to have poorer oral health than their nondisabled counterparts. Such children are unable to maintain their oral health by themselves; therefore they are completely dependent on their parents and/or caretakers for maintenance of their oral as well as overall health. Oral disease represents a major health concern among the children with disabilities.

There is a wide variety of disorders which indirectly affects the oral health of the child and sometimes it is not feasible for the parent or caretaker to particularly take extra care of oral health of such child. Generally, the birth of a child brings many expectations and celebrations, as well as doubts and anxieties concerning health, life and future in any family. These feelings are more intensified when parents are notified that they have a disabled child. In such situation, the parents often encounter difficult periods, due to the emotional factors, physical fatigue, mental stress and trauma.

DOWN SYNDROME

Down syndrome is a congenital autosomal anomaly which is characterized by generalized growth and mental deficiency. The risk for this chromosomal aberration is one out of every 600-1000 live births. It is widely assumed that the DS complex phenotype results from the dosage imbalance of the genes located on HSA21. The products of these genes act directly or indirectly, by affecting the expression of disomic genes.

The genetic nature of DS together with the relatively small size of HSA21 encouraged scientists to concentrate efforts towards the complete characterization of this chromosome in the past few years. The identification and characterization of HSA21 genes may improve our understanding of the molecular basis of the disease. Even before the complete sequence of 21q was determined, an intensive work started towards the characterization of HSA21 genes.

Dental caries development is considered to involve a triad of indispensable factors, which can be concluded as bacteria in dental plaque, carbohydrates in diet and susceptible teeth.

Some syndromes, which have chromosomal abnormalities reported to be associated with low caries indices. Down syndrome is an example of this condition.

This low caries incidence in children with Down syndrome is in spite of the presence of increased risk factors for caries such as cariogenic diet, decreased salivary flow rate, mouth breathing, imbalanced occlusal forces, and poor access to oral hygiene.

Experiences of Mothers and Child with Down's Syndrome

Parents play a vital role in caring for and rearing their children – even more so if it is a child with Down's syndrome. Parents react differently to their child's impairment. Raising a child with Down's syndrome leads to changes in the lifestyle of the whole family.

Identification and acceptance of learning disabilities are difficult processes, and promoting the child's optimal development require adaptation by all family members, whose characteristics, as well as the degree of affiliation and support among them, have great influence on these lifestyle changes, both in terms of quality and quantity.

Gallagher says some parents will accept the impairment more easily than others and will carry out the task of caring for the child more cheerfully with greater devotion. Others may feel isolated and distressed and may experience chronic sorrowfulness.

Most of the research studies on the experiences of families who have a child with a disability indicate that, although there may be commonalities in the parenting experiences, the impact differs considerably among families.

While parental functioning has been extensively examined in families with a child with a disability (e.g., Cuskelly, Jobling, Chant, Bower, & Hayes, 2002; Ricci & Hodapp, 2003; Roach, Orsmond, & Barrett, 1999), few studies have investigated parental experience specifically in families where there is a child with fragile X syndrome.

While stress is not the only impact on parents of having a child with a disability, it is one of the constructs central to our understanding of their experience and of parental functioning. In essence, stress is a negative (usually, but not restricted to) psychological response to demands that are perceived to be greater than the resources available to meet them (Lazarus, 1993).

Higher levels of stress have consistently been found to occur among parents of a child with a disability when they are compared to parents whose children are all developing typically.

The higher levels of stress found in parents of children with a disability have been assumed to be a product of the increased demands they experience.

These increased demands arise from the care needs of the child and the necessity to interact with and manage the child's environment (broadly defined and including hospitals, therapy settings and schools) in order to have the child's needs met. Both these areas of demand may be affected by the nature of the child's disability.

In a recent study comparing mothers of children with Down syndrome, fragile X syndrome, and autism, Abbeduto et al. (2004) found that mothers of a child with fragile X syndrome displayed lower levels of well-being than mothers of children with Down syndrome, but higher levels than mothers of children with autism.

In a recent study, the strongest and most consistent predictors of maternal depression and pessimism across three disability types (Down syndrome, fragile X syndrome and autism) were the extent and severity of the behavioural symptoms of their adolescent child.

Quality of Life of Mothers Having Children with Down's Syndrome

According to the definition of "quality of life" by WHO, life includes people's own perception of their position in life and in the cultural-value system in which they are living.

In systemic approach, family is considered a general system and the function of each of the family members affects the whole family system. The presence of a psychological disorder can eventually affect the whole system.

Simultaneously, it can affect the quality of life dimensions such as the parents-children relationship, relationship with peers, career relationships, personal transition, and environmental structure (Ahmadi, Khankeh, Rahgozar, Teymouri, & Sheikhona, 2013).

Children with Down syndrome have special needs that challenge parents to prepare the best for their future. These children can have profound effects on families (Ravindranadan & Raju, 2008).

Parents of children with developmental disorders experience high levels of stress, health problems, loss of feeling responsible and defect in physical functions, and fatigue or burnout.

Parents of children with Down syndrome are encountered with a lot of problems and stress due to their children (Amirmajd & Sareskanrud, 2012).

Among the most important issues of this disease is the burden imposed on their families. Their medical problems, including cardiovascular problems, respiratory, nervous, endocrine, gastrointestinal, surgical, orthopedic, eye and blood safety, and even multiple admissions impose a lot of costs to the family (Evans & Gray, 2000).

Also, their maintenance and training, particularly with respect to their behavioral problems and low IQ will require additional costs and activities. According to studies, financial and social problems in tolerance and adaptation to new roles and responsibilities of parents are important (Hemmati, Asadi, & Mirsepasi, 2005).

This condition is worse in third world countries, where families have limited resources and parents, especially mothers are unable to adequately address other aspects of life.

Additionally, parents of children with disability are exposed to a lot of stressful factors for a long time that puts them in an inconvenient and inefficient conditions, leading to problems in their marital relationships, career, and relationships of parents with other children and finally can have negative consequences for children (Jalili et al., 2013).

These mothers show high levels of stress (Paster, Brandwein, & Walsh, 2009), mental health problems, depression, anxiety, financial difficulties, negative emotions, self-blame, fear of child's future problems (Zani, Merino, & Marcon, 2013), impaired physical performance, and fatigue or exhaustion. Taking care of children with Down syndrome brings along fatigue, time consumption, and stress for the parents.

However, research shows that parents of these children more easily get used to this condition, because children with Down syndrome have positive features and less behavioral problems than children with other disabilities (Amirmajd & Sareskanrud, 2012; Oliveira & Limongi, 2011).

Permanent presence of mothers in the centre, long distances, high transportation costs for these children, the children's medical training, lack of funding for treatment, treatment from the organizations, lack of information and activity during the visiting hours can be among the factors that have a negative impact on the lives of mothers and cause low environmental health score. Parents of children with Down syndrome have higher stress and depression than normal parents. Many parents think of the child's disability as a sign of their own failure.

When parents fail to achieve these goals and become aware of the child's intellectual disability, they would face double mental pressure which affects their mental health (Malekpour, Farahani, Aghaei, & Bahrami, 2006).

These limitations may be due to the negative attitude toward certain diseases, little information of the society, cultural conditions, and specific situation of the children. Since the demographic variables in this study explained only 17% of the "quality of life" of mothers of children with Down syndrome, it seems that other variables could affect the "quality of life".

CEREBRAL PALSY

Cerebral palsy is a condition caused by damage to the brain, usually occurring before, during or shortly after birth. 'Cerebral' refers to the brain and 'palsy' refers to a disorder of movement or posture. Cerebral palsy is a central nervous system (CNS) disorder of

movement, coordination, and posture, reflecting a non-progressive abnormality or insult to the immature brain. One of the most common forms of neuromuscular disabilities affecting children is cerebral palsy (CP), the worldwide incidence being 2 to 2.5 per 1000 live births. Providing oral care to people with cerebral palsy requires adaptation of the skills we use everyday.⁵

Quality of Life of Mothers Having Children with Cerebral palsy

In the literature, studies investigating quality of life of mothers of children with cerebral palsy and related factors report different findings. It affects the mothers negatively which are reported mostly associated with depression. In a study performed by Diwan et al. 70% of mothers with CP children were reported to have mild-to-moderate depression, which was reported to have a negative effect on quality of life of mothers.¹⁰ Kaya et al. reported that the deterioration of mental health in mothers with children suffering from cerebral palsy gives rise to experiencing further low back pain by mothers, which leads to more deterioration in quality of life of mothers.¹¹ Keller et al. in one of their study stated that disability in children was reported to decrease social activities of their mothers and to have an influence on routine deterioration.¹²

Oral health care measures for Children with Cerebral palsy

It is important to keep utmost oral hygiene in children with cerebral palsy. Brushing twice daily using a soft and stable mouth prop. Dental visits and topical fluoride application every 6 months is must. Use fluoridated toothpaste; for children less than 3 years old use a smear amount of fluoridated toothpaste and for children above 4 years old use a pea size amount. Parents should monitor dietary habits (i.e. avoid prolonged use of bottle, reduce amounts of sugar consumed, reduce frequency of sugar consumed).

EPILEPSY

Epilepsy is a disease that involves seizures which are characterized by an alteration of perception, behavior and mental activities, as well as by involuntary muscle contractions, temporary loss of consciousness and chronic changes in neurological functions that result from abnormal electrical activity in the brain.⁶

Seizures can be defined as the discontinuity of normal brain functions due to sudden electrical discharges which may be either excessive or inadequate; these result in episodic

convulsions (such as involuntary motion), disturbances in perception, or alterations in consciousness. The outcome of such excessive discharge during electrical conduction is called seizure.⁶

Chapman et al. have reported that, epileptic seizures are the second most common medical incident in dental surgeries. They have stated that statistically every dentist notice in his/her professional life 1.5 times generalized tonic-clonic seizures by the patients. Epilepsy has been observed most frequently in children under 1 year of age. Up to 50% of children displaying mental retardation have been diagnosed as suffering from epilepsy.⁶

Quality of Life of Mothers Having Children with Epilepsy

As per the study performed by Aggrawal et al. (2011), Self esteem and social interaction scores of the children with mothers who were highly educated showed scores lower than the children with illiterate mothers.¹³ A. Pekcanlar Akay et al. in their study investigated how the disease and treatment of epilepsy affected the psychological profile (depression and anxiety) of mothers whose children had epilepsy. They found that the mothers scored significantly higher in depression and state anxiety. They also failed to develop supportive and friendly relationships with their children. In addition, these mothers also scored significantly higher in the Attitude of Hostility and Rejection, Marital Discordance and Authoritarian Attitude was also observed in some of the cases.¹⁴ Behavior problems and attention deficit problems are commonly seen in children suffering from epilepsy. Rodenburg et al. (2006) in his study demonstrated that parental psychopathology was significantly correlated with both internalizing and externalizing behavior problems in children with epilepsy.¹⁵

AUTISM

Autism spectrum disorders (ASDs) are lifelong neuro-developmental disabilities that begin in infancy and impair communication and social behaviours. The realization that there is no cure for the disorder may serve to increase parenting stress. Such children have delayed or inexistent verbal skills, difficulty in developing social relationships, inflexible adherence to rituals, mental retardation, resistant to changes, repetitive movements.

Quality of Life of Mothers Having Children with Autism

In a study by Rezendus et al in 2011, mothers of children with an autism diagnosis reported more stress than mothers of children with pervasive developmental disorder-not otherwise specified (PDD-NOS). In a recent study comparing mothers of children with Down syndrome, fragile X syndrome, and autism, Abbeduto et al. (2004) found that mothers of a child with fragile X syndrome displayed lower levels of well-being than mothers of children with Down syndrome, but higher levels than mothers of children with autism.¹⁶

As per study by Giallo et al., they observed increased levels of stress, sleep deprivation and fatigue have been associated with parents of children with ASD and are likely to compromise their mental and physical functioning. Parenting a child with autism involves additional challenges because of children's communication difficulties, self-care limitations as well as their unpredictable and aggressive behaviours as stated by Montes & Halterman (2008). A study by Hastings et al. (2005) has identified four key coping dimensions which are relevant to parents raising an autistic child which include active avoidance coping, problem-focused coping, positive coping, and religious/denial coping. DeVoe et al. 2007 stated that higher income could improve the physical environment for parents and increase access to health services for both child and parent whereas in study conducted by Attree in 2004, low-income parents' experiences of service support are often negatively reported and parents may appear reluctant to seek help for themselves or for their children. Parents should ensure that they have the time for themselves as well as children and enough resources to be able to participate in social and other health promoting activities which in turn will be beneficial in promoting their quality of life. The provision of respite care, experienced child-care at home, as well as support in planning outdoor activities with or without the child might be useful steps towards this direction.¹⁷

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